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Years of Life Lost for Exposure to PM2.5 in Europe

Between 2005 and 2020 they decreased by 59% on average for the countries considered

The Eurostat calculates the value of the "Years of life lost due to the PM2.5 exposure". The indicator takes into consideration the years of life lost due to the exposure to PM2.5 particulates. These are particulates with a diameter of less than 2.5 microns that can be transported in depth in the lungs where they can cause inflammation and aggravate the condition of people who suffer from heart and lung diseases. Years of Life Lost-YLL or years of lost life is a variable defined as the potential life that has been lost due to premature death. It is an estimate of the average number of years that a person would have lived if he had not died prematurely.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the years of life lost due to the PM2.5 exhibition in 2020. Italy is in the first place for the value of the years of life lost due to the PM2.5 exhibition with a value of 462,233 Unit, followed by Poland with an amount of 415,773 units and Germany with an amount of 296,305 units. In the middle of the standings there are Belgium with an amount of 36,174 units, followed by Austria with an amount of 30,587 units, and followed by Portugal with an amount of 25,829 units. Luxembourg close the rankings for an amount of 811 units, followed by Estonia with an amount of 688 units, followed by Finland for an amount of 683 units. On average, 89,315 years of life were lost due to the exposure to PM2.5.

Ranking of European countries by percentage variation of the value of the years of life lost for exposure to PM2.5 between 2005 and 2021. Poland is in the first place due to percentage variation of the value of the years of life lost for exposures to PM2.5 between 2005 and 2021 with an amount of -22.87% equal to an amount of -123,279 units, followed by Italy with an amount of -38.24% equal to an amount of -286,295 units, and by Slovakia with a amount of -41.02% equal to an amount of -32,088 units. In the middle of the standings there are Lithuania with an amount of -59.92% equal to an amount of -23,846 units, followed by Germany with an amount of -60.61% equal to an amount of -455,894 unit and from Austria with An amount of -47,400 units. Sweden's ranking close with an amount of -90.09% with an amount of -30,269 units, followed by Estonia with a value of -92.50% equal to an amount of -8,485 units, followed by Finland with an amount of -95.47% equal to an amount of -14,397 units. On average, the value of the years of life lost for exposure to PM2.5 between 2005 and 201 was decreased by 59% equal to an amount of -94,411 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimization with Elbow method. Followed by a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is presented. Five Clusters are therefore identified or:

- Cluster 1: Denmark, Estonia, Ireland, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Austria, Portugal, Slovenia, Slovakia, Finland, Sweden;
- Cluster 2: France;
- Cluster 3: Germany, Italy, Poland;
- Cluster 4: Spain, Romania;

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- Cluster 5: Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Netherlands.

In addition, it is possible to identify the following system of the Clusters on the basis of the median or: C3> C4> C2> C5> C1. From the geographical point of view it is clear that the countries that have the greatest value of years of life lost for exposure to PM2.5 are Germany, Italy and Poland, while the countries that have the lower levels of the observed variable They are the Scandinavian countries.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the Euclidean distance. Specifically, two network structures are identified, of which a simplified and a complex.

The complex network structure has the following characteristics:

- Malta has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.01 units, and with Estonia with an amount of 0.034 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Malta for an amount of 0.01 units and with Estonia for an amount of 0.034 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Malta for an amount of 0.034 units and with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.034 units, with Ireland for an amount of 0.068 units, with Cyprus for an amount of 0.067 units and with Finland for an amount of 0.059 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.067 units, with Finland for an amount of 0.051 units, with Ireland for an amount of 0.041 units;
- Finland has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.059 units, with Cyprus for an amount of 0.051 units and with Ireland for an amount of 0.065 units;
- Ireland has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.068 units, with Cyprus for an amount of 0.041 units, and with Finland for an amount of 0.065 units.

In addition, there is the following structure with simplified network or:

- Slovenia and Latvia have a connection for an amount of 0.067 units.

Conclusions. The value of the years of life lost due to the exposure to PM2.5 between 2005 and 2020 decreased from an amount of 4,867,590 units up to a value of 2,411,515 units or a reduction equal to an amount of - 2,456,075 units equal to an amount of -50.45%. Considering that in 2020 the value of the pro-bench income was equal to an amount of around 28,000.00 euros, it follows that in terms of value in 2020 around 65.5 billion euros were lost. Between 2005 and 2020 around 1.5 trillion of euros were lost. The fight against climate change has produced very positive results in Europe. There are still too many unnecessary deaths due to pollution. The orientation of European economic policies for environmental sustainability could further reduce the number of years of life lost for exposure to PM2.5.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

C3>C4>C2>C5>C1

- C1
- C2
- C3
- C4
- C5

Rank	Country	2020	Rank	Country	2020
1	Italy	462.233	15	Austria	30.587
2	Poland	415.773	16	Portugal	25.829
3	Germany	296.305	17	Lithuania	15.948
4	Romania	234.049	18	Slovenia	11.880
5	France	175.908	19	Denmark	11.249
6	Spain	164.653	20	Latvia	9.139
7	Bulgaria	108.001	21	Cyprus	6.084
8	Hungary	103.179	22	Ireland	5.941
9	Greece	86.214	23	Sweden	3.331
10	Czechia	68.744	24	Malta	1.738
11	Netherlands	49.832	25	Luxembourg	811
12	Slovakia	46.129	26	Estonia	688
13	Croatia	40.413	27	Finland	683
14	Belgium	36.174			